

Towards the sustainable giga-factory: developing green cell manufacturing Processes

Work Package 7

D7.1 – Dissemination and Communication plan

Lead Contractor: SIE

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS	5
2.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
3.	INTRODUCTION	6
3.1	Context of WP7	6
3.2	Objectives of T7.1	6
4.	OBJECTIVES	6
5.	TARGET AUDIENCES	7
6.	KEY MESSAGES	8
7.	TOOLS AND CHANNELS	9
7.1	Project identity	10
7.2	Project website	11
7.3	Social media	11
7.4	Printed material	12
7.5	Newsletters and press releases	16
7.6	Peer-reviewed articles	16
7.7	Conferences and events	16
8	INDICATORS AND TARGETS	17
9	LEVELS OF DISSEMINATION	18
9.1	European Level – European Commission	18
9.2	International level – Industry, Scientific community	18
10	METHODOLOGY	19
10.1	Internal Communication	19
10.2	External communication	19
11	METHODOLOGY	20
11.1	Phase 1: awareness phase	20
11.2	Scientific cooperation phase	20
11.3	Exploitation-focused phase	20
12	ACTIVITIES M1-M6	20
12.1	Project identity and materials	20
12.2	Press releases	21

12.3	Website	22
12.4	Social media.....	23
12.5	Newsletter	25
12.6	Events attended	26
12.7	Interaction with other EU initiatives	27

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1. Acronyms and abbreviations

OS Open science

CINEA	European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
WP	Work Package
KER	Key Exploitable Result
HE	Horizon Europe
DC	Dissemination and Communication
SIE	Sustainable innovations
M	Month
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
R&I	Research and Innovation
RM	Raw Materials
AM	Active Materials
CMEM	Cell manufacturing & equipment manufacturers
BPS	Battery Packs & Systems
OEM	Application & Integration
RSL	Recycling / Second Life
SC	Scientific community
PM	Policymakers
STC	Standardisation Technical Committees
GP	General Public
TM	Trade Media

2. Executive summary

GIGAGREEN proposes a structured research plan to develop and scale up novel electrode and cell component manufacturing processes that follow a Design to Manufacture approach in line with Europe's strategic goal of becoming a global leader in the Li-ion battery value chain.

This means that GIGAGREEN seeks for the minimum environmental impact and energy consumption, cell designs which facilitate the re-use and disassembly, increase of the cost-efficiency and safety of processes and products, and high-throughput technologies able to be easily scaled up and automated in the context of industry 4.0/5.0 gigafactories.

All tasks expected for the period were accomplished on time: social media online (M1), templates and promotional materials (M1), first press release (M1), website released (M2), first newsletter (M3), clustering activities (initiated M5 an ongoing) and attendance to events (M1 and ongoing).

3. Introduction

This document describes the Dissemination and Communication Plan to be adopted by the GIGAGREEN project, whose main objective is to ensure that the project's outcomes (concepts, scientific results, validated work, problem awareness) are consequently disseminated to appropriate target communities.

3.1 Context of WP7

The main aim of WP7 is to coordinate the project consortium in the performance of dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities, including IP management. Following the Open Science (OS) approach of the project, partners will maximise the openness of results and the interaction with sectoral stakeholders in a balanced way with IP protection measures established where necessary to ensure the proper exploitation of project KERs. The Consortium will contribute, upon invitation by the CINEA, to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between HE/H2020 supported actions.

3.2 Objectives of T7.1

A detailed Dissemination and Communication Plan (D&C) has been produced by SIE at the beginning of the project (M6), based on the preliminary indications given in Section 2.2 and in collaboration with all the consortia. It outlines the project's audiences, key messages, and communication channels for the dissemination, including roles and responsibilities. The different updates of the plan will offer the monitoring of the different dissemination and communications activities carried out by all partners, evaluated against its KPIs.

4. Objectives

In order to deliver and achieve the outcomes and impacts of the project, GIGAGREEN has set a specific plan for the dissemination, usage, and valorisation of research and innovation results. This document includes outreach efforts to inform the public about the utilisation of European funds for R&I projects,

social issues, the results of a sustainable and cutting-edge cell manufacturing sector in the EU. Thus, improving the communication between science, business, and society. WP7, "Dissemination, exploitation, and communication," will take the lead on these efforts, liaising with the other partners to ensure the greatest impact is made, and delivering a comprehensive Dissemination, exploitation, and communication Plan by M6. Here is a brief explanation of the main components of this proposal.

5. Target audiences

A sizable list of stakeholders has been initially established by GIGAGREEN for whom the distribution and communication tools and materials will be intended. Although the vehicle manufacturing sector is an established industry, the electric vehicle one and the associated deployment of the cell manufacturing ecosystem in Europe is not. This, which justifies the value chain strategy used in the project, which is typical of fast expanding industries. According to the [European Battery Alliance](#), the following table lists the key players in the value chain along with the key findings that will be shared with them throughout the project.

Table 1. Target groups & contents

Targeted results/content	Target group / Stakeholder
Design to manufacturing guidelines and data driven software / Enhanced cell manufacturing, bringing down costs along the value chain	Raw Materials (RM), Active Materials (AM), Cell manufacturing & equipment manufacturers (CMEM), Battery Packs & Systems (BPS), Application & Integration (OEM, Recycling / Second Life (RSL)
Optimised cell component materials for dry and wet processing / New 3b gen components for high power/energy density	RM, AM, CMEM
Novel wet and dry electrode processing techniques / Demonstrated manufacturing techniques to become market frontrunners in the next 10 years.	CMEM, BPS, OEM
Recycling process / Circular loops enabled within the factory, minimising material inputs	RM, AM, CMEM
Knowledge, reproducibility, etc.	Scientific Community (SC)
Standardisation, public roadmaps actualisation, etc.	Policy Makers (PM), Standardisation Technical Committees (STC)
EC funds, R&I efforts to enable affordable electric mobility.	General Public (GP)
Europe at the forefront of the battery industry, leading gigafactory construction: employment, reducing costs, boosting local and regional economy, etc.	Trade Media (TM)

GIGAGREEN has identified a significant list of target groups to which the dissemination and communication materials and tools will be directed to, as outlined in Table 1.

Table 1 summarises how the different stakeholder groups will be benefited from the project's results, The dissemination and communication strategy will conduct a thorough value chain analysis to better understand the influence and stakeholder interests, and to better adjust the key messages to deliver and how to do so, increasing the likelihood that the project's findings will be disseminated and used.

GIGAGREEN consortium members have preliminary identified a list of key associations and organisations that will allow to enhance the project’s results dissemination through mutual collaboration: [LiPLANET](#) (Network of battery cell Pilot Lines in Europe), [European Battery Alliance](#), [EMIRI](#), [ALISTORE](#), [EMMC](#) (European Materials Modelling Council), [BEPA](#) - BATT4EU Partnership, [BATTERY 2030+](#), [European Digital SME Alliance](#), and [ERMA](#) (European Raw Materials Alliance).

Consortium partners are a good reflection of the European battery value chain, including research centers, manufacturers, producers, and academia. Nevertheless, GIGAGREEN’s intention is to widen its collaboration with other relevant actors from the industry. Thus, a preliminary stakeholder list was prepared, including more than 300 organisations. This list will be regularly updated, and stakeholders will be informed on the project regular outcomes.

Likewise, similar European and international projects have been identified to seek for synergies: [3beLiEVe](#), [SeNSE](#), [COBRA](#), [HYDRA](#), [MODALIS2](#), [COFBAT H2020](#), [SPIDER](#), [ASTRABAT](#), [Bigmap](#), [BatWoman](#), [greenSPEED](#), [NoVOC](#), [NEXTCELL](#). GIGAGREEN has created a dedicated section on its [website](#), so stakeholders can easily access all their information.

Finally, a set of trade media contacts was listed, including the most relevant magazines: [Autobuild](#), [Autofacil](#), [Automotive news](#), [Autopista](#), [Autovolt](#), [Batteries and energy stories news](#), [Batteries International](#), [Battery Power Magazine](#), [Car and driver](#), [Charged electrical vehicles magazine](#), [Clicacoches.com](#), [Electrek](#), [Electric and hybrid world](#), [Electric cars report](#), [Electric Hybrid vehicles magazine](#), [Electrical India](#), [Energy Magazine Australia](#), [EV Magazine](#), [Inside EVS](#), [KM 77](#), [Motor 16](#), [Motor authority](#), [Motortrend](#). Also, project partners are expected to generate at least 10 peer review articles targeting Journals like [Journal of Materials Chemistry](#) or [Journal of Power Sources](#), as well as the open access site from the EC [Open Research Europe](#).

6. Key messages

The GIGAGREEN project will produce a significant amount of knowledge across five technical WPs, sparking interest across the value chain for cell batteries as well as the vehicle industry. The outputs and messages from produced WPs, as well as the suitable instruments and channels for distribution, must be identified. The essential messages from each WP are displayed in Table 2 below. Additionally, the primary target group(s) and distribution channels are established. The consortium group will keep spreading information about its overall goals and partnership engagement in anticipated activities. This includes private business meetings, presentations to possible clients, and scientific materials, milestones, etc.

Table 2. Key messages

WP	Key message	Target group / Key channels
Design to manufacturing	Digitalisation processes allowing for quicker specification change	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, PM
Wet and dry processing pathways development	High performance cells in terms of voltage, capacity, life cycle Elimination of organic solvents	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC
Scale up of the cell manufacturing processes	Cell manufacturing cost reduced by 20%	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM, PM

	Reduced energy consumption of cell manufacturing by 25%	
Electrochemical characterisation, and thermal, ageing and safety tests	Data driven process and product quality control	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC
Sustainability analyses and recycling process development	Affordable scalable processes	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM, PM

7. Tools and channels

The actions carried out by GIGAGREEN and its results will be disseminated and communicated using a variety of methods and means. The Dissemination Plan will be more effective since each instrument and channel will be used effectively to speak to various target groups at various stages of the project execution. Table 3 shows the connections between the target audiences, the tools and channels, and the anticipated outcomes.

Table 3. Tools and channels

Channels	Tools	Target group	Expected impacts
Printed materials	Brochure	All target groups	Create awareness about the project goals and expected impacts
	Leaflet		
	Poster		
	Rollup		
Online	Website	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM, PM	Keep the audience engaged on the project objectives and outcomes, as well as on achievements, and news.
	Newsletters	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, GP, TM, PM	
	Social media	GP, AM, RM, SC, PM, CMEM, OEM, TM	
Publications	Scientific papers	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, PM	Guarantee knowledge transfer
	Articles	All target groups	Generate interest in the cell battery production and the state-of-the-art technologies developed by GIGAGREEN
	Press releases	TM	Regularly inform trade media on the project outcomes and how this impact positively in European lives in

			terms of employment, technology development, improvement of environmental footprint, etc
Events organised by GIGAGREEN	Workshops	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, PM	Create awareness about the project goals and expected impacts
	Webinars		
Events attended by GIGAGREEN	Conferences	RM, AM, CMEM, BPS, OEM, SC, STC, PM	Keep the audience engaged on the project objectives and outcomes, as well as on achievements, and news.
	Tradeshows		

The project website, articles written for both a lay and technical readership, press releases, e-newsletters, scientific papers and booklets, social media presence, and attendance at workshops and conferences are some of the methods and channels proposed to be employed in this plan.

The dissemination plan described in section 2.2 of the Grant Agreement serves as the foundation for all efforts involving communication with stakeholders outside the project consortium. The goal of journal articles is largely to inform the academic and scientific communities of current discoveries. To spread new pertinent solutions to more potential end consumers, the project will also publish in key trade publications and magazines. The same audience is targeted for project presentations at technical conferences.

The European logo will be displayed along with the disclaimer that the project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe initiative in all dissemination efforts and publications, including the project website. The European emblem will be given the proper prominence when shown alongside a logo.

7.1 Project identity

In order to build a visual brand, a distinctive project identity has been created. It provides a set of templates that will make it easier to gain reputation as the project progresses. This involves developing the project's logo and the related style guide. Additional communication materials have been developed and made available on the project [website](#). This includes the project roll up, poster, factsheet, brochure, and presentation.

Image 1 GIGAGREN brand guidelines

Color palette

#FFFFFF	#E5E5E5	C 50	#D9EAD3	C 25	#A6C9EC	C 75	#80C080	C 90
R 255	R 200	M 40	R 180	M 30	R 150	M 20	R 100	M 40
G 255	G 140	Y 40	G 165	Y 55	G 185	Y 40	G 110	Y 60
B 255	B 130	B 0	B 125	B 0	B 145	B 0	B 100	B 4
#00788F	#A78777	#258058	#002D28					

Text/background/icon

#E5E5E5
#D9EAD3
#A6C9EC

Background/graphic elements

Font setting print & desktop presentation

Title 1 Bold 24pt Futura std	#2E8B58	Abcdefghi
Subtitle 1 Regular 16pt Futura std	#4C9691	Abcdefghi
Titre 3 Bold 12pt Futura std	#007568	Abcdefghi
Text Regular 11pt Futura std	#002D28	Abcdefghi
Figures Regular Italic 11pt Futura std	#838d86	Abcdefghi

Font setting web (Google font)

Title 1 Bold 24pt Montserrat	#2E8B58	Abcdefghi
Subtitle 1 Regular 16pt Montserrat	#4C9691	Abcdefghi
Titre 3 Bold 12pt Montserrat	#007568	Abcdefghi
Text Regular 11pt Montserrat	#002D28	Abcdefghi
Figures Regular Italic 11pt Montserrat	#838d86	Abcdefghi

Iconography style

Photography style

7.2 Project website

The GIGAGREEN project [website](#), has been created and it will be continuously updated to be appealing for visitors. It was made available on M2 of the project life and serve as main repository of the project information and outcomes.

For the time being, it has four main sections:

1. **About.** This tab contains information on the project goals, approach, and implementation. It also counts on GIGAGREEN's partners logos and description, as well as the most relevant related initiatives and associations.
2. **Downloads.** GIGAGREEN has made available the main resources till today: [brochure](#), [poster](#), [factsheet](#), [presentation](#), [logo](#) and [roll up](#). There, visitors can also find the first [press release](#) and [newsletter](#) issued.
3. **News.** In this section, the project will inform stakeholders about the latest updates on the project progress, interviews, and events at where partners will disseminate GIGAGREEN.
4. **Contact.** Whoever might be interested in reaching out GIGAGREEN, here they can simply fill out the form and contact the consortia.

7.3 Social media

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To ensure greater diffusion to various age groups and target audiences, GIGAGREEN will have a social media presence on [Twitter](#) and [LinkedIn](#). Social media should be utilised to promote project updates and, most significantly, to increase website traffic.

In order to broaden reach, GIGAGREEN-related content has been posted often starting in M1 on Twitter and LinkedIn. When the project has video content, a YouTube channel will also be made available.

In order to create an audience for the project results, the social media accounts will distribute updates about the project scope and promote events where GIGAGREEN will be showcased throughout the first phase of the project.

Online media platforms will be supervised to gather data on the metrics, sources, content kinds, and people or organisations who support or spread project messaging. This information will enable communication to be targeted and optimised for maximum reach of news or results. The final dissemination report and interim reports will both include these findings. SIE will be responsible for the social media profiles, assisted by partners.

Consortium members will follow and participate as much as they can in the project's social media platforms. The partners will frequently share posts on their own corporate websites and social media platforms. SIE can advise them on the most effective ways to do so if they require support.

Table 3 Milestones suitable to be communicated

Milestone	WP	Lead partner	Date
Validated Digital Twin	2	Leclanché	M30
Cell component selection	3	CiCe	M33
500 mAh pouch cells	3	CiCe	M43
First batch of 10 reproducible Large 10 Ah cells	4	ABEE	M40
Full cell passing abuse/aging tests	5	Polito	M42
Efficient Recycling Process	6	Inegi	M40

7.4 Printed material

To be distributed at conferences, exhibitions, and other events, as well as to partner networks, a [poster](#), a [roll-up](#), a [factsheet](#), and a [brochure](#) have been created. General information regarding the research activities, participants, and anticipated outcomes is included in the initial project poster and brochure version. Later in the project life, other materials could be created to publicise findings.

Image 2, 3, 4 GIGAGREN brochure, poster, factsheet

PROJECT PARTNERS

FOLLOW US ON SOCIAL MEDIA

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GIGAGREEN proposes a structured research plan to develop and scale up novel electrode and cell component manufacturing processes that follow a Design to Manufacture approach in line with Europe's strategic goal of becoming a global leader in the Li-ion battery value.

This means that **GIGAGREEN** seeks for the minimum environmental impact and energy consumption, cell designs which facilitate the re-use and disassembly, increase of the cost-efficiency and safety of processes and products, and high-throughput technologies able to be easily scaled up and automated in the context of industry 4.0/5.0 giga-factories.

DESIGN TO MANUFACTURE GIGA-FACTORY CONCEPT

SAFER
- Elimination of organic solvents

CHEAPER
- Reduced energy and material consumption, economy of scale
- Cell manufacturing cost reduced by 20%

GREENER
- Reduced energy and material consumption
- Energy consumption of cell manufacturing reduced by 25%

FLEXIBLE
- Digitalization processes allowing to quicker specification change
- Affordable scalable process

BETTER
- High performance cells in terms of voltage, capacity, life cycle
- Data-driven process and product quality control

GIGAGREEN will finalise by the end of the project with a set of novel materials (binders, electrolyte, separators, cathode, and anode active materials, etc.), adapted to innovative dry and wet electrode processing techniques, which motivate the generation of Design to Manufacture guidelines and a data-driven Digital Twin.

GIGAGREEN proposes a sustainable and cost-efficient new approach by integrating synergies and materials within the recycling and production chain of the new battery systems. Apart from recycling the metals (Cu, Ni and Al) and plastics, **GIGAGREEN** aims to recycle both active materials and electrolyte.

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GIGAGREEN

10%
Increase
Productivity

25%
Reduction of
Energy Consumption
& Carbon Footprint

20%
Reduction
of Costs

0%
volatile organic
compounds
generated

 [gigagreen-project](https://www.linkedin.com/company/gigagreen-project)

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7.5 Newsletters and press releases

Every six months, electronic newsletters containing project updates, news, interviews, and other GIGAGREEN-related information will be created. These newsletters will be sent to stakeholders and partner networks as well as uploaded on the project website.

Additionally, project updates could be included in the partners' own newsletters, which are sent electronically to the contacts they have within the relevant industries.

Press releases will be released to announce noteworthy project advancements as they happen. With the support of the project partners, they will be written in English and distributed to the national media and the European press.

7.6 Peer-reviewed articles

The technical and academic partners will create at least 10 scientific papers, bringing additional benefits like greater transparency in the research process, better opportunities for new scientific collaborations, and increased efficiencies in research. The project's findings will be disseminated both internationally in international journals like [Journal of Materials Chemistry](#) or [Journal of Power Sources](#), as well as nationally, primarily in the Member States where the partners are based. Open Research Europe is an open access, free of cost alternative as well for partners.

Likewise, the project website will compile all publications and make them available for free download.

7.7 Conferences and events

To meet target audiences, other stakeholders, public authorities, and the scientific community, project partners will attend sector-related events, conferences, and workshops. They will also spread the word about the project's goals and outcomes. Access to target audiences at the local, national, European, and worldwide levels will be made possible by these events.

The following conferences and trade shows have been pointed out as being of interest to the GIGAGREEN project:

- [Advanced Battery Power](#). April 2023
- [Therminic](#). September 2023
- [Thermal management for EV/EHV](#). November 2023
- [Future Battery Forum](#). November 2023
- [International Motor Show](#). October 2023
- [E-MOBILITY WORLD](#). March 2023
- [The Battery Show Europe](#). May 2023
- [Electric & hybrid vehicle technology expo](#). May 2023
- [Vehicle Electrification Expo](#). June 2023
- [Automotive Testing Expo](#). June 2023
- [Green Vehicle Expo](#). June 2023
- [Life Cycle Innovation Conference](#). August 2024
- [5th International Conference on Battery and Fuel Cell Technology](#). October 2023
- [International Electric Vehicle Symposium and Exhibition](#). June 2023

- E MOVE 360° EUROPE. October 2023

In order to ensure that the project is present at events for dissemination, this list of events will be updated often in partnership with the consortia.

Along with attending conferences and trade shows, GIGAGREEN will collaborate with other initiatives under the same call to host at least two workshops by the end of the project to address standardisation and policies, as well as four other webinars to raise awareness on the different project propositions.

8 Indicators and targets

The accomplishment of particular targets for various indicators will serve as a gauge for how well the Dissemination and Communication Plan is being implemented.

Table 4 Indicator and targets

Tools / channel	Indicator	Target number	Information source
Brochure Poster Factsheet	Number of copies distributed	Material distribution: <300 poor; 300-500 good; >500 excellent	Consortium information, number of copies distributed to target groups / stakeholders
Website	Number of visits	Visits per year: <600 poor; 600 – 1,200 good; >1,200 excellent	Website statistics
Social media (Twitter, LinkedIn)	Number of followers Number of impressions Engagement rate	Twitter; (a) Followers: < 100 poor; 100 – 200 good;> 200 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <0.2% poor; 0.2% - 0.9% good; > 0.9% excellent LinkedIn; (a) Followers: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent. (b) Engagement rate: <2% poor; 2- 3% good; >3% excellent	Social media analytics
Videos	Number of views Audience in conferences /trade shows	At least 2 in the project. Views: <100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >200 excellent	YouTube, website and social media analytics Attendance to booth /conference
	Number of subscribers Number of opens	At least one each six months. Subscribers:	Mailchimp (newsletter service),

Newsletters	Visits from website / social media	<100 poor; 100 – 200 good; >300 excellent Opens: <15% poor; 15% – 17% good; >17% excellent	Website and social media analytics
Press releases	Number of media stakeholders addressed Number of views on website and social media	At least 4. 100 media sources / journalists reached Number of views: < 40 = poor; 40-60 = good; >60 = excellent	Recording of e-mails sent, Website and social media analytics
Scientific publications	Number of views/downloads	10 publications	Link to site where posted or PDF version of article
Workshops	Number of attendees	1 standardisation + 1 policy feedback workshop. Number of attendees each: <15 = poor; 15-25 = good; >25 = excellent	Registration list
Webinars		4 webinars. Number of attendees: <25 = poor; 25-45 = good; >45 = excellent	Registration list /webinar platform analytics
Conferences Trade fairs	Number of conferences and trade fairs attended Number of exhibitors and participants	Attend 24 conferences	Certificate of participation; Proof of registration; Event information

9 Levels of dissemination

The geographic levels at which the main target groups operate will affect the communication methods and media used.

9.1 European Level – European Commission

The results of the project will be reported to the EC on a regular basis (mid-term review, minutes of periodic meetings, updates to this document) so that it can make any necessary changes to the relevant regulations and suggest collaborating with other projects that are already in progress on dissemination efforts.

9.2 International level – Industry, Scientific community

The outcomes will be communicated to the pertinent international organisations. Scientific knowledge can be converted into useful information, regulations, and guidelines. Electronic resources will be distributed by direct mailing to specified organisations and stakeholders in order to increase public awareness.

For the transmission of knowledge at both the research and industrial levels, technical journals, conferences, and workshops at both the national and international levels, industry meetings, and participation in industrial forums will also be utilised.

10 Methodology

To make sure that the GIGAGREEN outcomes are effectively and efficiently conveyed to the project partners, stakeholders, and wider audiences, the following internal and external communication activities will be carried out throughout the project's duration and afterward.

10.1 Internal Communication

To effectively share information and guarantee that the deliverables are met, effective internal communication is essential. Therefore, to exchange project information, update progress, and share outcomes, frequent meetings and conference calls will be held. Two times a year, consortium and technical meetings will be held, and WP collaboration will be facilitated through the use of Microsoft Teams and/or teleconferencing tools.

Apart from individual emails, taking advantage of the project monthly conference call, SIE will ask partners for their support on the upcoming dissemination and communication activities and events to update the Communication & Dissemination Plan and expedite a content curating process. As a result, the partners will be better able to communicate and report on the project while also adopting a more methodical and focused approach. Each GIGAGREEN consortium partner will send a representative to this meeting.

Politecnico di Torino has also set up a Microsoft SharePoint space, which will host the project materials for internal use, including regular updates on the project development, meeting documents (agenda, minutes, and presentations), and project reports. This will help partners communicate effectively with one another.

A login name and password will be required to access this exclusive area.

10.2 External communication

The consortium will make every effort to spread the word about its activities through the media, journals, conference presentations, trade shows, workshops, the Commission, and industry associations. The project's findings will be published in reports, academic publications, and articles. To encourage scientific collaboration, all public communications and scientific publications shall be made open access.

The partners will send SIE the text whenever a translation is required, and SIE will take care of modifying the design.

11 Methodology

As the project has different development phases, the communication focus would be different across each of them.

11.1 Phase 1: Awareness phase

In this phase, GIGAGREEN will prioritise the generation of a community of interested stakeholders and of suitable channels. It will comprise from months 1 to 12.

11.2 Phase 2: Scientific cooperation phase

This second phase will consist of knowledge management for the cooperation of GIGAGREEN with similar projects and initiatives and ensuring the availability of research outputs to targeted audience. It will start in M6 and will last for the project duration.

11.3 Phase 3: Exploitation-focused phase

This phase will cover the support to the actual exploitation of project results via marketing towards final end users (commercial results) or workshops and roadmaps (non-commercial results) and will comprise the final stages of the project (M24-M48).

12 Activities M1-M6

12.1 Project identity and materials

During the initial stage of the project, GIGAGREEN's visual identity was developed. It contained the project's logo and the brand guidelines (typography, colours). A project presentation, a roll-up, a poster, and a variety of other communication tools were also created. The partners were provided with a template for the deliverables, a Word document template, and a PowerPoint template.

As soon as the website was online, the first brochure, poster, factsheet, roll-up, and project presentation were uploaded:

Image 5 Word template

12.2 Press releases

A press [release](#) was launched at the beginning of the project. It was sent to more than 200 local and trade media by SIE and several consortium partners.

Image 6 GIGAGREEN's first press release

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The GIGAGREEN project kicks off to achieve the future sustainable giga-factory

- *GIGAGREEN is a project financed with almost €4.7 million by the European Union under the Research and Innovation Framework Programme Horizon Europe aiming at developing sustainable and safe cell manufacturing processes for Li-ion batteries.*
- *The initiative is supported by a multidisciplinary consortium of 16 partners comprising research centres, universities, consultancy companies, material suppliers, and cell manufacturers from 8 European countries.*

Turin (Italy), September 22. GIGAGREEN, a project financed by the European Union (EU) under the Research and Innovation Framework Programme Horizon Europe willing to develop sustainable and safe cell manufacturing processes, has just kicked off with a meeting held in Turin (Italy).

For 48 months, GIGAGREEN, formed by 16 partners from 8 different European countries, will work to achieve the sustainable giga-factory of the future, positioning Europe at the forefront of the global market in the Li-ion battery value chain, key for the next generation of electric vehicles.

The project proposes a structured research plan to develop and scale up novel electrode and cell component manufacturing processes that follow a Design to Manufacture (DTM) approach to attain the intended goals.

In this sense, GIGAGREEN will seek electrode manufacturing processes which deliver the maximum performance, throughput rate, safety and cost efficiency at the lowest environmental impact and energy consumption in the cell design, also facilitating the reuse and disassembly. The DTM approach, supported by digital solutions as Digital Twins, will allow for the development of easily scaled up and automated concepts solving the needs for the upcoming generation of European cell giga-factories.

In summary, GIGAGREEN will bring a tipping point for the EU cell manufacturing industry, as its outputs have been thought to contribute to a smooth transition between today's processing methods – optimised by trial-error approaches and not ready for flexible mass production – and the Li-ion cell Factory of the Future – one based on greener, cheaper, safer, better, cleaner, digitalised, and flexible technologies.

GIGAGREEN thrives in the interfaces of the current and the new manufacturing approaches. It focuses on those points of greatest urgency: cell-electrodes processing and components that represent the highest energy and economic costs with a larger room for improvement and ground-breaking innovation.

Thanks to the advancements brought by GIGAGREEN, the EU industry will be able to (i) quickly use the results regarding water-based processing after 2026 so the performance of the industry starts immediately improving its competitiveness with materials designed and improved to operate and be processed under those conditions, and (ii) start paving the path towards dry electrode processing techniques as the next Li-ion manufacturing technology revolution.

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The total impacts for this type of communications reached 74 outlets in total, including media, consortium partners and related projects portals, as shown in Annex 1.

12.3 Website

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The website www.gigagreen.eu was launched on M2 with essential information of the project and will be updated constantly with progress and news from the project and partners.

Apart from the sections mentioned above, regarding the News section, 6 posts about the project scope, participation of the consortium partners in events and interviews have been uploaded:

- <https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1034>
- <https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1039>
- <https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1233>
- <https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1313>
- <https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1323>
- <https://gigagreenproject.eu/archivos/1317>

Image 7 GIGAGREEN's website analytics

12.4 Social media

The LinkedIn account: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/gigagreen-project> and the Twitter account: <https://twitter.com/GIGAGREEN> were created and updated with content on a regular basis since the project's kick off.

During this period, 50 publications were shared, reaching out up to 33 followers, and our publications got a total of 4,463 impressions on Twitter, as of January 17.

Image 8 GIGAGREEN's Twitter account

Activity also begun on LinkedIn on September 2022. In this period, and until January 17, 17 posts were published, achieving 287 followers. The publications reached 21,133 impressions.

Image 9 GIGAGREEN's LinkedIn network

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12.5 Newsletter

In M4, the first Newsletter was released as shown in Image 10.

Image 10 GIGAGREEN's Newsletter

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Towards the sustainable gigafactory: developing green cell manufacturing processes

GIGAGREEN project kick-off took place in Turin (Italy) on September 22 and 23.

GIGAGREEN, a project financed by the European Union (EU) under the Research and Innovation Framework Programme Horizon Europe willing to develop **sustainable and safe cell manufacturing processes**, kicked off with a meeting held in Turin (Italy).

For 48 months, GIGAGREEN, formed by 16 partners from 8 different European countries, will work to achieve the sustainable gigafactory of the future, **positioning Europe at the forefront of the global market in the Li-ion battery value chain**, key for the next generation of electric vehicles.

[Read more](#)

OBJECTIVES

GIGAGREEN will bring a tipping point for the EU cell manufacturing industry, as its outputs have been thought to contribute to a smooth transition between today's processing methods – optimised by trial-error approaches and not ready for flexible mass production – and the Li-ion cell Factory of the Future – one based on **greener, cheaper, safer, better, cleaner, digitalised, and flexible technologies**.

12.6 Events attended

During M1-M6 of the project, the different GIGAGREEN members have attended 4 events to speak about the project to internal and external audiences:

1. NanoInnovation. CICE Energigune. September 2022.
2. Battery Weekly. Manz Italy. November 2022

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3. Kunststoffe für Brennstoff Zellen und modern Batterietechnik (Plastics for fuel cells and modern battery technology). Arlanxeo. November 2022
4. Wired Italia Trends 2023. Politécnico di Torino. December 2022.

12.7 Interaction with other EU initiatives

GIGAGREEN has already established contact with the projects under the same call: BATWOMAN, GREENSPEED and NOVOC, and a first meeting was held in January 2023 to discuss about possible future actions to carry out together. Likewise, Politécnico di Torino and SIE met with BEPA to seek for possible future synergies in November 2022.

A dedicated section on the website to inform about these projects is also available on GIGAGREEN's website. Later, on M7 a website was created to contain relevant information about all projects on <http://www.batteryheroes.eu/>.

Image 11 Related initiatives meeting

13 Impact on media outlets and other relevant websites M1-M6

ABEE

<https://abeegroup.com/projects/>

ACLIMA

<https://aclima.eus/gigagreen-un-proyecto-europeo-de-raiz-gallega-para-construir-gigafabricas-de-baterias-sostenibles/>

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ALPHANOV

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AGADIR GROUP

<https://agadir-group.com/gigagreen-consortium-designs-future-battery-cell-factories/>

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ATIGA

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AUTOREVISTA

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<https://www.bestmag.co.uk/automotive-skills-alliance-and-european-battery-alliance-academy-join-forces-to-bridge-battery-supply-chain-skills-gap/>

CANAL ENERGÍA

<https://www.canalenergia.com/rubriche/think-tech/trasferire-produzione-di-batterie-da-asia-a-europa-al-via-gigagreen/>

CETIM

<https://cetim.es/gigagreen-hacia-la-gigafabrica-de-baterias-sostenible/?lang=en>

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VLC TECH CITY

<https://twitter.com/VLCTechCity/status/1570089365518303234>

